

From Wrist to Twin: A Well-being Centered Human Digital Twin for Amateur Athletes Using Smartwatch Wearables in Society 5.0

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Abstract. Society 5.0 envisions a human-centered cyber-physical society in which digital and physical systems enhance well-being and productivity. In this context, consumer smartwatches provide affordable, semi-continuous monitoring that can support a practical Human Digital Twin (HDT) for amateur athletes balancing training, recovery, sleep, work, and social demands. Advances in edge-cloud computing and analytics have enabled wearables to provide automated insights such as excess post-exercise oxygen consumption (EPOC)-based training load estimation, VO_2max trends, and multi-sensor sleep tracking. However, evidence suggests that wearable outputs should be interpreted primarily as trends and general indicators rather than precise gold-standard measurements, especially during rapid physiological changes or high-movement activities. This paper proposes an HDT architecture for amateur athletes, a trend-first interpretation approach informed by validation literature and expert guidance, and a closed-loop model integrating habit formation, neuroplasticity, and gamification. The framework defines four adoption levels (L0–L3), with Level 3 supporting decision-making through converging trends in sleep quality, heart rate variability (HRV), resting heart rate (RHR), and acute training load rather than isolated measurements. Gamification features, including streaks, badges, and progress dashboards, are combined with habit-building strategies and reinforced through reward-learning mechanisms linked to dopamine prediction error signaling, creating a continuous feedback loop that supports sustained engagement and adaptive self-management.

Keywords: human digital twin, smartwatch, habit formation, wearables.

1 Introduction

Society 5.0 emphasizes human-centered cyber-physical integration whereby digital technologies improve everyday life and well-being. Human digital twins (HDTs) can be interpreted as personal, semi-continuously updated cyber representations that support decision-making in health, performance, and lifestyle domains [1]. Consumer smartwatches produce semi-continuous streams of physiological and behavioral data (e.g., heart rate, sleep metrics, HRV, training load, steps, etc.). For amateur athletes,

this creates an unprecedented opportunity: low cost, longitudinal monitoring that can support daily planning and sustainable training while balancing professional and personal demands [2-4].

The challenge of interpreting numbers as truth is central to the field of smartwatch metrics. Consumer wearable measurements vary across device models, contexts, and individuals [5]. Accuracy degrades during movement and rapid heart rate transitions, and many downstream metrics are derived through proprietary algorithms [6]. Multiple high-level reviews caution that absolute benchmark interpretation can be misleading, while trend interpretation and contextual integration can be valuable [1, 2, 7, 8].

Amateur athletes generally lack a coherent, validated, and practical framework that treats smartwatch metrics as trend indicators, converts trends into actionable routines, embeds habit formation and gamification into feedback loops, and addresses privacy, ethics, and responsible limits of interpretation [2, 9-11]. Responding to these limitations, this paper provides a four-level adoption model (L0–L3), an HDT architecture and metric tiering approach, a Level 3 habit loop grounded in behavioral theory and reinforcement learning, gamification design principles for well-being habits, and governance guidance.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the background and related work, followed by Section 3, which depicts the data landscape, and Section 4 presents the research methodology. Section 5 presents the HDT architecture and analytics framework, namely (1) the four-level adoption framework, (2) the well-being mechanisms, measures, and Society 5.0 alignment, and (3) the guideline framework. In Section 6, the authors discuss the findings and conclude the paper in Section 7.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Human Digital Twins (HDT) and Society 5.0

Recent HDT literature converges on architectures that link a physical individual to a dynamic virtual representation via semi-continuous sensing, analytics, and feedback. HDTs are increasingly framed as human-centered digital twins (distinct from industrial twins) that must handle neighboring concepts such as noisy data, behavioral complexity, and ethical constraints [1]. These neighboring concepts and the HDT describe how humans can be represented in cyberspace, where cyber-physical systems (CPSs) are designed to interact with humans in a personalized way [12]. The objective of the interaction is to establish interactions and decentralized collaborations under specific rules integral to the system. Individuals are synchronously contributing to the overall functioning of the system by collaborating to complete specific tasks. Therefore, individuals are not only the end users of a service but also cumulatively generate value for the community [13, 14]. Alternatively, the representation of humans in CPSs can be considered merely to generate knowledge on the individual; thus, the twinned individual(s) are granted limited access and control over the system and model [15].

2.2 Wearable Metric Validation and the Trend-First Principle

Growing validation literature finds that consumer wearables can provide useful estimates for some metrics under specific conditions; however, accuracy is context-dependent and often insufficient for clinical diagnosis or high-stakes performance decisions. A living umbrella review notes wide variability and incomplete validation coverage across device outcomes, while highlighting that many outcomes remain insufficiently validated relative to the breadth of marketed metrics [1].

Importantly, real-world validation work shows that wrist-worn devices perform worse during transient states (rapid HR changes), while larger averaging windows improve accuracy, supporting a trend/average interpretation stance [7]. Clinical guidance also discourages absolute interpretation of HRV from consumer wearables, recommending longitudinal trends integrated with context and history [2]. For sleep, state-of-the-science reviews emphasize the promise of longitudinal monitoring but caution that staging and fragmentation estimates remain limited. Basic sleep duration and timing trends are more reliable than detailed stage outputs [11].

Consumer ecosystems increasingly operationalize training load through Excess Post-Exercise Oxygen Consumption (EPOC)-based models and rolling windows (acute load) that support planning and recovery guidance. These metrics are best interpreted as decision aids rather than physiological ground truth, and are strengthened by combining them with sleep and perceived exertion [16, 17].

2.3 Habit Science, Implementation Intentions, and Feedback Loops

Habit formation research shows that repeated behaviors in consistent contexts become increasingly automatic, often following an asymptotic curve. This insight supports designing HDT loops around stable cues, tiny actions, and repeatable routines [1, 11]. Implementation intentions (“if-then plans”) reliably improve goal enactment by delegating control to cues (“If situation X occurs, then I do Y”), aligning naturally with smartwatch prompts and calendar-based actuation.

Dopamine reward prediction error (RPE) theory explains how unexpected positive outcomes strengthen future behavior [18, 19]. Modern reviews extend classical RPE theory to broader learning signals, but the central insight remains—feedback that exceeds expectation reinforces behavioral updating [4, 20]. In the HDT context, visible progress trends (e.g., improved sleep consistency, lower resting HR at the same pace) act as reinforcing signals that can sustain habit repetition [11, 20, 21].

Experience-dependent neuroplasticity principles (specificity, repetition, salience, intensity, and time) provide a biological rationale for structuring training and lifestyle habits as progressively reinforced routines rather than sporadic, heroic efforts [9, 22, 23].

2.4 Gamification and Health Behavior Change

Systematic reviews show that gamification elements (goals, points, streaks, challenges, and feedback dashboards) can improve physical activity and adherence, though effects

vary by design and population. Meta-analytic findings indicate small-to-moderate improvements in activity with gamified interventions, especially when personalization and feedback are present [3, 10, 24, 25]. Critically, reviews also caution that gamification must be designed thoughtfully to avoid short-lived extrinsic motivation and becoming a distraction, rather than a facilitator [26]. Well-designed systems support competence, autonomy, and relatedness, rather than solely badges [9, 27].

2.5 Dark Data and Knowledge Management

Dark data refers to data that are collected and stored but never meaningfully reused. Dark data is commonly unstructured, hidden in legacy systems or backups, and often escapes the attention of operational and sustainability teams, making it simultaneously costly and easy to ignore [28].

Dark data is not only a value-loss problem but also a sustainability problem. Storage and processing of unused data impose energy and cooling burdens on data centers, contributing to the carbon footprint of digital systems [28]. This perspective is directly relevant to consumer wearables. Smartwatches generate continuous multi-sensor streams that far exceed what most amateur users engage with. Moreover, recent umbrella-level evidence shows that only a fraction of wearable device outcomes is comprehensively validated, while devices generate many derived metrics. This combination encourages passive accumulation and low trust in underuse [2, 24].

Therefore, researchers treat dark data as both an adoption barrier (the data exist but do not translate into action) and a design opportunity (curate and surface a minimal set of reliable trends and cues that reinforce healthy routines). This becomes a central design feature of the Level 3 HDT [8, 23, 28].

3 Data Landscape

The target user is an amateur athlete with competing demands (professional work, family, and travel), training three to six times per week, with a non-uniform routine and limited stability. This profile differs from that of elite athletes with coached programs and controlled recovery [3]. Smartwatch exports provide rich multi-modal activity records (activity type, date/time, distance, calories, duration, average/max HR, cadence, pace, ascent/descent, and respiration), enabling longitudinal analysis of training and lifestyle rhythms.

3.1 Dark Data in Smartwatches

A large portion of wearable data is collected but is not meaningfully used. The framework aims to convert dark data into a small set of stable trends that drive actionable routines and habits [29]. In the smartwatch context, dark data comprises the large share of captured information that is (a) never seen by the user, (b) seen but not interpreted, or (c) interpreted once (single-use data), but not connected to decision targets or habits. This includes high-frequency sensor streams (Photoplethysmography (PPG))

waveforms and beat-to-beat intervals), accelerometer/gyroscope traces, raw global positioning system (GPS) tracks, respiration samples, temperature proxies, and multiple derived metrics (sleep staging, stress scores, and readiness indices) that are often displayed as single numbers without transparent computation [8, 24, 30].

Dark data prevents action in three practical ways. First, it creates cognitive overload as users are presented with dashboards but not with decision-ready interpretations or priority cues, leading to “data rich, insight poor” behavior. Second, the opacity of proprietary algorithms reduces trust and promotes disengagement, especially when subjective experience conflicts with device outputs. Third, the absence of workflow integration (calendar prompts, if-then plans, and weekly review routines) means data are not converted into actionable knowledge, enabling repeatable behavioral change loops [16, 19, 31, 32].

A knowledge management (KM) lens reframes the smartwatch problem—the value of data is realized only when it is transformed into usable knowledge through socio-technical practices such as governance, measurement, organizational (or personal) learning, and decision automation [32]. In a personal HDT, these practices translate into minimizing storage and focusing on a few reliable trend variables, capturing context notes through short diary logs, and using the trend signals as cues within habit and gamification loops [8, 23, 28].

Holding onto unused data is not benign and has disadvantages. Maintaining such data incurs costs (financial, operational, and environmental) since storage systems use energy even when no insights are generated [28]. This perspective typically applies to organizations but is equally relevant to consumer ecosystems and cloud services that accumulate vast amounts of personal sensor data without providing clear benefits to users. At a personal HDT level, a practical approach is to limit unnecessary data retention, such as keeping summaries rather than raw data streams when appropriate, while also promoting transparency and user control [33].

4 Methodology

This paper seeks to design and operationalize an HDT architecture suited to amateur athletes through design science research (DSR). DSR is a problem-solving paradigm that aims to enhance human knowledge by addressing real-world problems through the creation of innovative artifacts [34]. Specifically, the approach suggested by Hevner [35] was followed, consisting of three cycles: the relevance cycle (understanding the requirement in the application domain), the rigor cycle (grounding the artifact design in the existing knowledge domain), and the design cycle (building the artifact). In terms of the relevance cycle, the aim is to address the real-world problem, namely that amateur athletes lack structured, actionable frameworks for wearable data. Sections 2 to 4 summarized the rigor cycle, drawing from the scientific foundations, experience and expertise, and meta-artifacts in published literature. In the rest of the paper, we execute the design cycle, presenting and discussing the design artifacts, a practical utility, and a usable framework for amateur athletes.

5 Human Digital Twin Architecture and Analytics

This section describes the typical data pipeline from the body, through the sensors, to the data. It tenders ideas on algorithms for trend development, artificial intelligence (AI) applications, and metric quality tiers. The architecture consists of several key components: sensors, edge models, cloud aggregation, trend analytics, a decision engine, and actuation through calendars or prompts—all culminating in governance. This structure mirrors the operational dynamics of existing consumer ecosystems. However, its uniqueness lies in the focus on interpreting trends first, integrating habit formation with gamification elements, and implementing transparent decision-making policies [7, 8, 10, 21].

Evidence indicates that wrist-worn devices exhibit reduced accuracy during transient conditions and during exercise, but their average values and long-term trends are sufficiently stable for self-monitoring and planning [1, 7, 21]. For HRV, clinical guidance discourages absolute interpretation and supports trend-based integration with history and context [2]. For sleep, evidence supports longitudinal monitoring but cautions against an over-interpretation of staging; duration, timing, and consistency trends are more reliable [11]. Modern devices embed algorithmic interpretation and deliver feedback at low marginal cost to the user. Data on workouts, estimating load, and summarized sleep and recovery trends are readily available. The real constraint for impact is not “more data” but integrating decision targets and workflows into daily life. This is echoed in practitioner commentary: many systems fail because decision targets and implementation loops are unclear [29].

When evaluating health and training metrics, it is important to categorize data into tiers based on their reliability and usefulness [36]. For HDT smartwatch devices, these tiers are proposed, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Data tiers for HDT smartwatch devices

HDT data tier		Description	Ref.
Tier A	More robust for decisions	Resting HR trends, weekly volume (time/distance), sleep duration consistency, and acute training load trend (rolling windows)	[1, 7, 11, 16]
Tier B	Useful heuristics, caution	Nightly HRV trends, composite readiness/energy scores, and stress indices (interpret as cues, not truth)	[1, 2]
Tier C	Limited; avoid strong claims	Sleep stages as precise composition, wrist SpO ₂ for clinical claims, and blood pressure claims from non-clinical wrist devices	[2, 11]

The KM framing of dark data as a socio-technical challenge can be used to develop a data-to-insight pipeline within the HDT [28]. In this context, design choices that limit complexity while strengthening actionability are required [33]. Fig. 1 illustrates a data-to-insight pipeline by integrating the HDT data tiers.

Fig. 1. HDT data-to-insight pipeline

Identify (Step 1) collates collected, but unused streams (e.g., sleep stages, stress, respiration) and marks that are likely to be reliable enough for trend monitoring rather than absolute judgement [8, 20, 30]. This collation is an input into triage (Step 2), where metrics are classified into Tier A/B/C and discard or downweigh Tier C metrics for decision-making. Only data points that support stable longitudinal interpretation are retained [2, 8, 30]. Curate (Step 3) compute rolling averages and deviations from personal baselines (e.g., seven-day / 28-day), and annotate anomalies with diary context (travel, workload, etc.). Scholars show that monitoring, combined with feedback, improves the effectiveness of behavior change compared to monitoring alone [17, 23]. Surface (Step 4) presents a small "decision panel" that converts trends into actionable recommendations (e.g., train hard / train easy / recover). This procedure addresses the "data increases, impact does not" problem when decision targets are unclear [16, 17, 31]. Lastly, Reinforce (Step 5) links surfaced trend improvements to habit and gamification rewards (e.g., streaks, progress bars, micro-badges) to strengthen repetition and long-term adoption. Systematic reviews indicate gamified mHealth interventions can improve physical activity outcomes, especially when feedback is present [22].

5.1 Four-Level Adoption Framework

A four-level adoption framework is proposed to present the differences between user levels and the adoption of smartwatch technology. This model aligns with similar adoption-level frameworks for technologies. A technology adoption framework is a structured methodology for analyzing, predicting, and guiding the acceptance and implementation of new technologies by individuals or organizations [37]. These models help manage risks, minimize resistance, and align technology with strategic goals, often focusing on key factors such as ease of use, utility, organizational readiness, and external market conditions [37]. Level progression corresponds to increasing cyber-physical coupling: from passive measurement to active behavioral control loops [29]. The proposed framework is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Proposed HDT Four Level Adoption Framework

Level		Descriptor
Level 0	Image / Perception	Wearable as identity and status, minimal interpretation, and no change loop. Dark data is invisible. The smartwatch is worn, and data accumulates, but the user rarely checks dashboards and never uses the data to change training or lifestyle. Value is symbolic, not behavioral.
Level 1	Informative	Basic dashboards, social sharing, steps, and workouts with little behavioral adaptation. Dark data is ignored or parked. Users view a few headline metrics (steps, calories, and distance), but most streams (sleep trends, HRV baselines, training load, and stress patterns) remain unused.
Level 2	Understand	Regular trend review and learning (sleep vs. training vs. stress), but inconsistent action. Dark data becomes selectively dim. Users start noticing patterns (e.g., poor sleep equates to worse training), but the absence of structured feedback loops and cue-based habits means insights do not consistently translate into action.
Level 3	Personal Best	Closed-loop self-management with plan-do-sense-analyze-adapt loops that are strengthened via habit design, gamification, and feedback reinforcement. Dark data is curated into decision data. Only a minimal set of high-value trend variables is retained and reviewed (sleep duration consistency, baseline HRV trend, resting HR, and rolling load). The HDT uses these trends to trigger implementation intentions, prompts, and gamified reinforcement that convert dark data into sustained behavior change.

Thus, Level 3 embeds a habit-loop engine shown in Fig. 2 into the HDT with a cue (stable prompt linked to time, place, or routine), followed by action (insignificant behavior with low friction, and finally, a reward (immediate feedback through check-off and a trend signal). Habit science supports such cue-driven automaticity through implementation, which operationalizes cue-action pairing, while reinforcement theory explains why visible improvements sustain repetition [1, 11, 20].

5.2 Well-being: Mechanisms, Measures, and Society 5.0 Alignment

Various well-being benefits arise from improved self-efficacy (clear daily decisions), reduced overreaching via recovery-aware load management, improved sleep hygiene through consistent routines, stress visibility and coping strategies, and cognitive offloading (lower planning burden) [2, 11, 21, 29]. A trends-based approach to improved well-being for amateur athletes is proposed with focus on Physical (injury-free adherence, pace trend at constant HR, or HR trend at constant pace), Recovery (sleep duration consistency; baseline HRV trend; resting HR trend) and Work/life aspects (daily diary rating [energy, focus blocks, stressors]) [2, 11, 21]. If this is implemented alongside a diary-analysis procedure to link normal work activities with the training and well-being objectives, the loop can support the development of new habits.

Fig. 2. The habit loop engine

5.3 Guideline Framework

Based on the background on smartwatch-based well-being metrics, trend-based data management, access to a wealth of well-being metrics, and diary data, a framework can be developed for amateur athletes using smartwatches to guide their training and well-being. Such a framework may have the following sections, as depicted in Table 3.

Table 3. HDT guideline framework [4, 9, 11, 19, 20]

Guideline	Guideline example
Daily Decision Policies Trend convergence rules (simple traffic-light policy)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Green</u>: sleep duration near personal norm + HRV within baseline range + acute load stable → proceed with planned training. • <u>Amber</u>: one signal degraded (sleep down OR HRV down OR unusual resting HR up) → shift to easy session or technique/mobility. • <u>Red</u>: multiple signals degraded for $\geq 2-3$ days → rest, active recovery, and prioritize sleep and stress management.
Weekly Planning Load shaping (weekly review focus)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rolling acute load trend. • Consistency of sleep. • Subjective fatigue and mood. • One small progressive overload target (e.g., + 5–10% volume). • One de-load week after three to four build weeks.
Dashboards and Diaries Human-in-the-loop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A one-minute daily diary that adds context with notes on, for example, travel, signs of illness, deadlines, and unusual stressors. • This improves interpretation and reduces the risk of false attribution to “the watch.” • Feedback and monitoring are consistently identified as key techniques in effective digital behavior change.
Risk Mitigations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid single metric decisions (especially composites).

Avoid over-trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prefer trend convergence. • Treat stage sleep as indicative, not diagnostic. • Use abnormal values as prompts for reflection or medical follow-up, not self-diagnosis.
Level 3 Habit Design Cue-Action-Reward + Gamification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habit formation is accelerated by implementation intentions, tiny actions to reduce friction, and gamification by capturing streaks, badges, progress bars, small challenges, and supportive social feedback. • Gamification works best when supporting autonomy/competence and not only extrinsic rewards, as reviews caution that poorly designed gamification can be superficial or short-lived.
Neuroplasticity-informed Progression + Dopamine reinforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neuroplasticity principles translate into habit design, focusing on specificity (target the habit you want), repetition (small daily consistency), salience (link to meaningful goals), and time (allow consolidation). • Positive trend feedback also aligns with dopamine reinforcement learning. When outcomes exceed expectations, reward prediction error signals support learning and repetition. Modern dopamine reviews confirm the centrality of prediction error learning while recognizing broader roles.

6 Discussion

The paper argues for a pragmatic Society 5.0 interpretation of the personal HDT, where the goal is not clinical precision, but human-centered decision support based on reliable trends, feedback loops, and habit formation. This stance is consistent with evidence that wearable accuracy is context-dependent. Trend/average monitoring is often more reliable than acute measurement, especially for HR/HRV in free-living contexts.

Clinical and elite sport settings often require validated instruments (benchmark), known uncertainty bounds, and professional oversight. Expert sports-science commentary reinforces that wrist-based metrics should not replace standard techniques in high-stakes settings, but can be valuable for general population awareness and trend tracking. Gamification meta-analyses show modest improvements in activity and body composition. Systematic reviews suggest that gamification can support engagement, especially when combined with personalization and meaningful feedback. The HDT habit engine provides a structure for gamification with purpose, linking points/streaks to well-being habits and correlations with work diaries, rather than vanity metrics.

Some limitations in the broader use of smartwatches as HDTs include proprietary algorithms that reduce transparency and comparability across brands, and sleep staging and fragmentation accuracy remain limited. Behavior change is complex, and wearables may enable, but do not guarantee, change without contextual integration, and the mere joy of exercise and the fundamental benefits of movement for the human body should not be negated through the focus on developing an HDT.

Some suggested future work in this area includes the empirical validation across a cohort of amateur athletes and the comparison across devices and algorithms. Another research direction is the development of explainable-AI overlays for transparency and the integration into university sport/well-being programs and staff workflows.

The cue-action-reward concept generalizes to non-human digital twins as event-process feedback loops. Process mining offers methods for discovering and evaluating real process behavior from event logs and can be used to create process habits (standardized responses to events) and conformance checking. This provides a conceptual bridge between personal HDT loops and organizational digital twin loops.

7 Conclusion

This paper presents a Society 5.0-aligned approach to a wearable-enabled HDT for amateur athletes. The central design principle is trend-first interpretation, where consumer wearable outputs are treated primarily as indicators of change over time and as triggers for reflection and behavioral adjustment. This approach is strengthened by explicit feedback loops, habit-forming mechanisms, and gamification designed for well-being rather than vanity. The framework lays the foundation for future empirical studies in accordance with appropriate ethics governance.

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